

< Instrument for early mastitis detection in goats >

Abstract: This research addresses the challenges in detecting mastitis in the goat dairy industry. Mastitis is a serious inflammatory condition of the udder typically caused by bacterial infection. Early detection and prompt treatment are essential for the damage management and prevention of the infection spreading within the herd. Due to the special physiology of milk glands in goats, it is not possible to unambiguously diagnose mastitis in goats based on the measurement of any single parameter, such concentration of somatic cells, milk electrical conductivity, temperature or milk yield as is the established practice of diagnosing disease in dairy cows. For accurate and early diagnosis of mastitis in dairy goats, BioSense Institute is developing an instrument that simultaneously measures 4 primary variables of milk, as well as an algorithm that processes primary variables and includes 4 secondary as well as 4 external variables. The novel instrument, integrating artificial intelligence and multiple variables, aims for over 90% accuracy. The study outlines a rigorous data pre-processing pipeline, involving transformations, feature selection, and multiple regression analysis. The electronics division into analogue and digital subsystems is discussed, showcasing the successful testing of Prototype 1.0 and improvements in Prototype 2.0. The mastitis symptom detection tool exhibits promise for proactive animal health management, early detection, and potential benefits for milk quality, animal welfare, and economic gains in the dairy industry. As the technology evolves, it holds the potential to revolutionize mastitis detection globally.

Keywords: <goats, sub/clinical mastitis, sensor, milk>

1. Motivation

The goat dairy industry grapples with challenges in detecting subclinical or clinical mastitis (further in the text *sub/clinical mastitis*), given the inflammation's subtle symptoms. Conventional methods for cows prove inadequate due to anatomical differences in goats [1,2]. Goat milk's apocrine secretion results in variable somatic cell concentration independent on mastitis status, hindering its application as a standard diagnostic tool. To address these limitations, there's a crucial need for novel instruments, extending beyond traditional milking parameters. Research suggests daily analysis of electrical conductivity (EC) milk and udder temperature, immediate milk yield, and animal physiology for a more comprehensive approach to mastitis detection [3]. The overarching motivation is to refine diagnostic tools, bridging gaps and contributing to enhanced monitoring systems in the goat dairy industry. The motivation is to find better and more tailored diagnostic tools for mastitis in goats, with a particular emphasis on designing the instrument beyond traditional milking-related parameters. Overall, the research seeks to address the unique challenges posed by mastitis in goats and contribute to the development of reliable diagnostic and monitoring systems for the goat dairy industry.

2. Research questions

First variable to analyse is electric conductivity of milk (EC). EC of goat milk is one of the parameters that needs to be studied intensively, since the knowledge about this topic is scarce. Romero et al. says that it is necessary to do daily EC measurements with algorithms, similar to dairy cows, and consider significant factors like individual variation. Specialized conductometers should be developed for incorporation into short milk tubes in goat clusters to enable EC measurement during milk flow, facilitating more precise studies [4]. Moreover, other researchers indicate that daily EC measurement, without specific thresholds, and comparison with previous readings can enhance the detection of health status characteristics, as well as the development of algorithms based on the gathered data [5,6].

Furthermore, mastitis symptoms in goats depend of multiple variables and hence, the tool must be upgraded to combine the conductivity measurements with other available data and will exploit artificial intelligence (AI) for data quantification. It is vital to measure daily milk and udder temperature and milk yield. Contrary

to marked available modules that measure only the conductivity, the novel module developed here should include additional variables, such as animal species, age, gravidity, season, feed composition and sample temperature [7-10]. Due to these multiple influential factors required for detection of mastitis in ruminants appears to reason for the absence of the sub/clinical detection tool on the market.

3. Methodology

Primary variables that instrument measures in situ (mounted on milking parlor) are EC, milk and udder temperature, milk yield and ambient temperature. The instrument will daily gather data and with other available data to exploit AI for data analytics (Figure 1.). The goal with this instrument is to reach accuracy levels of over 90%.

Following data collection and categorical-to-numerical transformations on explanatory variables, a comprehensive data pre-processing stage will be conducted. This involves various transformations and removal of correlated variables based on statistical analysis. To address noise, linear or non-linear filtration will be applied. Data normalization will then be performed to eliminate dynamic range differences in explanatory variables' significance. The final step includes applying transformations (Principal Component Analysis or feature selection) to reduce explanatory variables. Feature vectors (x) will be created, and Multiple Regression will be applied to a pre-processed dataset, divided into training, validation, and test parts. Parameters of multiple regression models will be estimated in the training set, tested on the validation set, and weight factors for variables are obtained. After being tested on the test set, the model will have a new pre-processing round begins, followed by model training-validation-testing iterations if accuracy falls short. This iterative process continues until satisfactory weight factor estimation and prediction accuracy are achieved.

Figure 1. Flow chart of signal workflow

4. Solution/Discussion

All primary variables are pre-processed in the sensors conditioning circuits (calibration and normalization) – a low-level signal processing and normalization, i.e. adjustment dynamic range and subsequently digitalized in A/D converter for further processing in μ -controller ESP32. The digital signal next will be sent in JSON format via http POST service to the cloud. The electronics of the tool are divided into two subsystems, an analogue and a digital one, each serving specific functions related to data acquisition, sampling, calculations, and communication with external servers. Prototype 1.0 underwent rigorous laboratory testing and on-farm trials, demonstrating its robustness and functionality under practical milking conditions (Figures 2 and 3). The new Prototype 2.0 has several necessary changes in terms of speed and functionality upgrades, as well as the addition of display and barcode reader (Figure 4).

Overall, this tool ought to bring advances in early detection of mastitis in small ruminants. Hence, it holds great promise for the dairy industry, offering a proactive approach to animal health management and, which will lead to improved milk quality, animal welfare, and economic benefits for farmers. As this technology continues to evolve and undergo real-world testing, it has the potential to revolutionize mastitis detection practices and positively impact the dairy sector on a global scale.

Figure 2: Mastitis symptom detection tool scheme (left) and 3D picture of the tool (right) (Prototype 1.0)

Figure 3: Mastitis tool testing in different farms in Serbia

Figure 4: Mastitis tool with the barcode reader and display (Prototype 2.0)

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Acknowledgments:

This work is supported through ANTARES project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement SGA-CSA. No. 739570 under FPA No. 664387. <https://doi.org/10.3030/739570>

This work is also supported through Code: Re-farm project that has received funding from European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101000216.